

IBID 2023

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12th International Biotech Innovation Days
17/10/2023 – 19/10/2023
Open Access (Free of Charge)

BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg, Senftenberg, Germany
Konrad-Zuse-Medienzentrum (Building 11)

<https://www.b-tu.de/ibid/>
Contact: ibid@b-tu.de

IBID is an international open access conference where basic research and industry meet to discuss the latest topics across disciplines in a lively setting.

17.10.2023	18.10.2023	19.10.2023
Cancer biology & diagnostics	Biosensors, Bioanalytic & Bioinformatics	Regeneration & Immunomodulation during Aging
<i>In vitro</i> systems for toxicology and drug testing	Neurodegenerative Diseases	Poster Session & Poster Award
	Brandenburg Health Science Talks	Young investigator career seminar
	Social Dinner	

Organizers: Julia von Maltzahn | Franziska Dinter | Manuela Rossol | Stefan Rödiger

Dear Colleagues,

On behalf of the IBID Organizing Committee, we welcome you at the International Biotech Innovation Days 2023 (IBID 2023) open access conference at the Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus – Senftenberg.

This year we are focusing on cancer diagnostics, biosensing, biological analysis techniques, bioinformatics, neural disorders research, tissue regeneration strategies and altering immunity in aging.

The symposium is organized by the BioResponse e. V., members of the BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg and supported by Berlin Partner for Business and Technology GmbH.

The goal of the symposium is to bring attendees up to date on the latest clinical and scientific findings and to facilitate networking with members of the medical and scientific communities, as well as policymakers and industry representatives, to engage in stimulating dialogue and explore current trends, breakthroughs and potential solutions in their respective fields. As in all previous symposia, new findings will be presented and methodological aspects discussed.

We hope you enjoy the opportunity to hear presentations from distinguished keynote speakers, participate in discussions and poster presentations, and network with peers. Key topics include novel approaches to tumor detection, advanced sensor systems for monitoring toxins, refined analytical techniques, computational methods for analyzing disease patterns, exploring the pathophysiology of neurological diseases (collaboration with the NeuroMir consortium), implementing interventions for regeneration, and investigating immunological adaptations associated with aging.

Participants will benefit from this multidisciplinary forum where they can network, share expertise and explore opportunities for collaboration.

We would like to thank all those who have supported this symposium financially or in an advisory capacity, as well as the active participants who will present their latest results. We expect that our 12th IBID Symposium will stimulate a broad debate on how the new achievements from laboratory work can contribute to the improvement of diagnostics and therapy of diseases. We hope you will enjoy the scientific program and your stay in Senftenberg.

Yours sincerely,

Franziska Dinter, Julia von Maltzahn, Manuela Rossol, Stefan Rödiger

Senftenberg, 10/17/2023

NeuroMiR - Multiparametric bead-based detection of miRNA signatures of neurodegenerative diseases.

The RUBIN Alliance

The RUBIN alliance NeuroMiR (2021 – 2023, FKZ 03RU1U051F) combines core competencies from science and industry in the fields of antibody technology, multiparameter diagnostics, optoelectronics and microfluidics technology. With these competencies, the consortium will develop an innovative platform technology for precision diagnostics of neurodegenerative biomarkers at the microRNA and protein level. Through close collaboration, a complete value chain will be realized within the RUBIN alliance and commercialized worldwide.

In a nutshell: NeuroMiR technology is based on the simultaneous detection of miRNA and protein specific signatures for neurodegenerative diseases (focus on Parkinson's disease & Alzheimer's disease). The detection is performed using camel nano-antibodies. The reporter system operates in the infrared range to eliminate background signals. In addition, the detection reaction is performed in a hydrogel to delineate reaction spaces. The automation of the measurement is made by microfluidic (liquid handling) and the imaging platform.

The region

The NeuroMiR joint project links the German states of Berlin, Brandenburg, Saxony, and Thuringia. The focus of the alliance is on the Berlin/Brandenburg region. The spatial proximity to the state capital regions of Berlin, Potsdam, and Chemnitz as well as to the metropolitan areas of Eastern Thuringia (Gera) and Western Saxony offers ideal opportunities for further interdisciplinary cooperation.

In particular, the cooperation between the German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases and the Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin should be mentioned. The SMEs involved are characterized by many years of very successful cooperation with regional research institutions. They have extensive experience in translating scientific results into economically efficient products.

The greatest possible effect for the RUBIN region is the generation of a unique regional competence profile for the multiparametric detection of miRNAs. This gives the region a unique technological edge and competitive advantage.

The partners

The participating companies and research institutions with their respective core competencies within NeuroMiR are:

MEDIPAN GmbH

Development of an automated readout platform, commercialization of the platform.

Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg (BTU)

Development of multiparametric microparticle-based high-throughput methods

Askion GmbH

Development and certification of optoelectrical system solutions for bioanalytics

BiFlow Systems GmbH

Development of microfluidic diagnostic cartridges and microarray

GA Generic Assays GmbH

Development of test kits and positive controls for biomarker detection

PolyAn GmbH

Development and optimization of multiplex beads and immobilization

new/era/mabs GmbH

Production, characterization, and validation of camelid antibodies

University of Potsdam

Professorship for Immunotechnology (PIT) – Production, characterization, and validation of specific antibodies

German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases (DZNE)

Provision of biospecimens, evaluation of miRNA profiles, clinical expertise

The goals

The goal of the NeuroMiR alliance is to **enable routine and mass-market precision diagnostics for neurodegenerative diseases**. Compared to the state of the art, this method should be able to **deliver adequate results even at a very early stage**. This diagnostic approach will be realized by the **simultaneous detection of known and already clinically validated protein and miRNA markers**. This detection is made possible by a new state-of-the-art biomarker class, the circulating microRNAs (miRNAs). Until now, monitoring of these characteristic proteins and miRNAs has been associated with laborious bone marrow fluid collection, which is burdensome for patients. The NeuroMiR research alliance is developing a test system that can detect up to 30 different protein molecules and miRNAs indicative of **neurodegenerative diseases, even in a simple blood sample**.

The consortium is organized in two joint projects. In the first, the bead-based test kit to be used is being developed, by means of which the biomarkers can be made measurable via excitation in the near-infrared range. In the second consortium, a corresponding high-performance analysis device will be developed for use in corresponding laboratories.

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CLUSTER GESUNDHEITSWIRTSCHAFT BERLIN BRANDENBURG

Sessions with this symbol have a webex access
via <http://bit.ly/IBID> or the QR code

IBID Tuesday, October 17th 2023

Opening

09.45-09.50 Julia von Maltzahn, Manuela Rossol, Stefan Rödiger
Opening words
BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg, Germany

09.55-10.00 Gesine Grande | online
Welcome address by the President of BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg
BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg, Germany

Session 1: Cancer biology and Diagnostics

Chair: Stefan Rödiger

10.00-10.35 Björn Brücher (Keynote)
Molecular Carcinogenesis
European Academy of Sciences and Arts (EASA), Berliner Wissenschaftliche
Gesellschaft (BWG), Head GI Cancer Center, Carl-Thiem-Klinikum, Germany

10.35-10.55 Harald Schuhwerk
The plasticity factor ZEB1 at the crossroads of intratumor heterogeneity,
therapy resistance and anti-tumor immunity
Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany

10.55-11.20 Coffee Break

11.20-11.40 Sebastian Günther
Cytotoxicity of traditionally used Ethiopian medical plants
University of Greifswald, Germany

11.40-12.00 Dirk Roggenbuck
Loss of tolerance to glycoprotein 2 and association with autoimmune liver
disease and concomitant tumor disease
Medipan GmbH, Germany

12.00-12.20 Christian Linke
Quantification of mitochondrial cfDNA reveals new perspectives for early
diagnosis of colorectal cancer
Medizinische Hochschule Brandenburg Theodor Fontane, Germany

12.20-12.30 Eric Sädler
Single molecule melting curve analysis for characterization of methylation
markers in tumor diagnostics
Attomol GmbH, Germany

12.30-12.40 Victoria Liedke
Fully automated viability and toxicity screening – a reliable all-in-one attempt
BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg, Germany

12.40-13.45 Lunch Break

Session 2 : In-vitro and in-vivo test systems for toxicology and drug testing – 13.30-15.30

Chair: Steffen Braune

- 13.45-14.15 Ernst Michael Jung (Keynote) | online
Treatment of liver tumors: conservative – surgical: documentation of therapeutic success
Institute for Radiology, University of Regensburg, Germany
- 14.15-14.35 Dennis Kobelt
In vitro live cell imaging for testing new anticancer therapies to predict *in vivo* treatment efficacy
Experimental Pharmacology & Oncology Berlin-Buch GmbH (EPO), Germany
- 14.35-14.55 Andreas Pöbel
Evaluation of drug-induced liver injury (DILI) in a 96-well-plate-model vs. a human microphysiological liver model
dynamic42, Germany

14.55-15.30 Coffee break

- 15.30-16.00 Markus Frohme (Keynote)
In vitro test systems for tumor therapy
TH Wildau, Germany
- 16.00-16.15 Jan Willem Robering
Bombyx mori silk fibroin scaffolds as cell carriers for adipose tissue derived stromal cells
University of Veterinary Medicine Hannover, Germany
- 16.15-16.30 Anne-Sophie Fisch
Patient-derived organoids from head and neck cancer facilitate the investigation of individual responses to irradiation
Institute of Veterinary Anatomy, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
- 16.30-16.45 Tim Christer
Activability of rat platelets after silicone exposure in the closed-loop model
University of Veterinary Medicine Hannover, Germany
- 16.45-17.00 Tom Pietrobelli
Rapid and Reproducible Generation of Novel Immortalized Cell Lines
InSCREENeX GmbH
- 17.00-17.10 Marie Kristin Ulbricht (Speed lecture)
Lentivirus-mediated generation and characterization of MuSK-verexpressing HEP-2 cells for immunofluorescence-based diagnostics of Myasthenia gravis
BTU Cottbus – Senftenberg, Germany
- 17.10-17.20 Mahmood Sami Abdulqader Hanash (Speed lecture)
Influence of aqueous extracts of *Arthrospira platensis* on human liver cancer cells
BTU University Cottbus – Senftenberg, Germany

IBID Wednesday, October 18th 2023

Session 1: Bioanalytics / Bioinformatics - Neurodegenerative Diseases 09.00-12.00

Chair: Peter Schierack, co-chair: Stefan Rödiger

- 09.00-09.30 Michał Burdukiewicz (Keynote)
AmyloGraph: mapping the landscape of amyloid-amyloid interactions
Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain
- 09.30-09.50 Zoltan Cseresnyes
Quantifying the structure and function of organs-on-chip with artificial
intelligence-aided image processing
Hans-Knöll-Institute Jena, Germany
- 09.50-10.10 Patrick Steglich
Digital rapid tests enabled by photonic integrated biosensors
HyPhoX GmbH & TH Wildau, Germany
- 10.10-10.30 Jarosław Chilimoniuk
Imputomics: comprehensive R package for missing data imputation in
metabolomics data
Medical University of Białystok, Poland

10.30-11.00 Coffee Break

- 11.00-11.20 Sebastian Kersting
Modern diagnostically and digitally supported healthcare: The Fraunhofer
Center for Digital Diagnostics
Fraunhofer IZI-BB, Germany
- 11.20-11.40 Raphaëlle Lesage
Digital Twins and Simulations for Health Product Development: Current
Applications and Future Perspectives
esqLABS GmbH, Germany
- 11.40-11.50 Coline Kieffer
Multiplex and digital detection of microRNA using microfluidic droplets
and suspension arrays
ESPIC Paris, France
- 11.50-12.00 Mathias Schlegel
SeraSpot® Array on Demand - One Well. Many Opportunities
Seramun Diagnostica GmbH, Germany

12.00-13.00 Lunch Break

Session 2 : Biosensors / Bioanalytic / Bioinformatics - Neurodegenerative Diseases 13.00-15.00

Chair: Dirk Roggenbuck

- 13.00-13.30 Harald Prüß (Keynote)
Autoimmune encephalitis and dementia – new disease concepts
DZNE, Berlin, Germany
- 13.30-13.50 Annika Zink
Reprogramming-driven drug discovery identifies an efficacious repurposing
candidate for Leigh Syndrome
Universitätsklinikum Düsseldorf, Germany
- 13.50-14.10 Katarzyna Winek
The role of the immune response and the microbiome in ischemic stroke
Leibniz Institute on Aging, Jena
- 14.10-14.30 Michael Kirschbaum
Sorting cells based on their microscopic image information
Fraunhofer IZI-BB, Germany
- 14.30-14.40 Stefan Hirschberg
Chimeric virus-like particles (cVLP) for therapeutic and diagnostic antibody
development
Charité und preclinics certified products GmbH, Germany
- 14.40-15.00 Ingolf Lachmann
Future early diagnostic biomarkers of risks for development of Alzheimer's
dementia?
Roboscreen GmbH, Germany

15.00-15.30 Coffee Break

Session 3 : Brandenburg Health Science Talks 15.30–16.45

Chair: Jan-Heiner Küpper

- 15.30-15.40 Jan-Heiner Küpper
Introduction
Institute of Biotechnology, BTU Cottus – Senftenberg, Germany
- 15.40-16.00 Julia von Maltzahn
Muscle stem cells in age and disease
BTU Cottus – Senftenberg, Germany
- 16.00-16.20 Christian Kopkow
From cells to exercises – evidence-based physical therapy of osteoarthritis
BTU Cottus – Senftenberg, Germany
- 16.20-16.40 Stefan Rödiger
Multiparametric biosensor for the analysis of neurodegenerative diseases
BTU Cottus – Senftenberg, Germany

16.45 Get Together/Networking at the IBID 2023 venue

Snacks and drinks

Campus tours: 1. Institute of Biotechnology & 2. Institute for Health

19.30 Social Dinner at Restaurant *Drogerie* in Senftenberg

Since seats are limited, reservations were required, and seats were assigned on a first-come, first-served basis, please ask if your reservation was successful when you register

Jüttendorfer Anger 2, 01968 Senftenberg, Deutschland

If you unfortunately didn't get a seat, we recommend other restaurants/pubs in Senftenberg (e.g. Ristaurante & Pizzeria Due Fratelli (Italian), Restaurant Olympia (Greek), Irish Pub, Tiroler Stadl (German/Eastern cuisine), Restaurant LIDO (seasonal and regional), Restaurant Himalaya (Indian).

IBID Thursday October 19th 2023

Session 1 Regeneration and Immunomodulation during Aging: 9.00-11.05

Chair: Manuela Rossol, co-chair: Julia von Maltzahn

- 9.00-9.25 Romy Kronstein-Wiedemann
Novel evidence that the ABO blood group shapes erythropoiesis and results in higher hematocrit for blood group B carriers
Technical University, Dresden
- 9.25-9.50 Katja Uhlig
Colon cancer organoid-on-chip to investigate the efficacy of anti-cancer drugs by online monitoring of cell viability
Fraunhofer IZI-BB, Potsdam
- 9.50-10.15 Kristin Schubert
Linking molecular mechanisms to effects: How environmental chemicals disrupt endocrine functions in obesity and inflammation
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung, Leipzig
- 10.15-10.40 Julia Gross
Cellular decluttering - what extracellular vesicles tell us about cellular stress...
HMU Health and Medical University, Potsdam

10.40-11.35 Coffee Break

Session 2 Regeneration and Immunomodulation during Aging: 11.10-12.55

Chair: Julia von Maltzahn, co-chair: Manuela Rossol

- 11.35-12.00 Doreen Thor
Orphan G protein-coupled receptors as novel targets in obesity and diabetes
University of Leipzig, Leipzig

12.00–12.25 Franziska Knopf
An mpeg1+ macrophage subpopulations supports bone formation during
development and regeneration
Technical University, Center for Healthy Aging, Dresden

12.25-12.50 Gerd Kempermann
Technical University, CRTD, Dresden

12.50-12.55 Concluding remarks by the organizers

12.55-14.00 Lunch Break

Session 3 Poster Session and Poster Award: 14.00-15.45

Chair: The organizing Committee and Referees

Session 4 Karrierewege in den Gesundheits- und Biowissenschaften: 16:30-19:00

Location: Zukunftsteam Lausitz
Schmiedestraße 8 <https://www.karriere-lausitz.info/>
01968 Senftenberg

16.30 lockerer Start mit Begrüßungsgetränk und Snack

17.00-19.00 Roundtable Discussion

Poster Abstracts of International Biotech Innovation Days 2023

At the end of the booklet you will find poster abstracts for this year's International Biotech Innovation Days 2023. The abstracts show the title of the poster and are sorted in alphabetical order by the last name of the submitter. Each poster has a number as indicated in the booklet. A space for your poster will be allocated by the organizers on site with the corresponding number.

Schedule of poster presentations

Posters can be mounted starting 10/17/2023 and should remain mounted until 10/19/2023. The conference participants and jury can review the posters on all days. The breaks are a good time to discuss the posters with colleagues. On 19/10/2023 the poster session and the awarding of the poster prize will take place.

Poster Award

There are three poster prizes to be awarded this year. On the one hand, prizes will be awarded by the audience and, on the other hand, by a jury. A distinction will be made between young investigators (Bachelor, Master ..., PhD student) and senior scientists (postdocs, individuals in higher positions in a company) for the jury prize. The winners of the poster prizes will be announced on 19/10/2023 at the end of the poster session.

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MILESTONE 4: IMPLEMENTATION

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Alva Genomics

Location: Jena/Germany
Industry: bioinformatics
Web: alva-genomics.com
Contact: mail@alva-genomics.com

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Analysis of RNA-Sequencing Data: Next to mRNA, we also offer the analysis of small RNAs such as microRNAs.

Epigenomics Data Analysis: NGS-data of the epigenomic states of a cell to help associate identified genomic sites to phenotypic attributes. This include DNA-methylation (e.g. WGBS) or histone locations as well as modifications (e.g. ChIP-Seq).

Custom Software Solutions: Tailored bioinformatic pipelines (such as Nextflow or Snakemake) for reproducible and easy to use workflows.

The **BioResponse e.V.** of Lower Lusatia has teamed up with tech firms, diagnostic service providers, and academic and research institutions from the surrounding areas to establish a center of excellence for multi-parameter diagnostics. The organization aims to bring together the diverse skills of its members through core competency-based multi-parameter evaluation.

<https://www.bioresponse.de/>

Numerous innovative multi-parametric applications for routine diagnostics and applied research will be achieved by the BioResponse technology. Developing a scientific concept for multiparametric analytics will help marketing and sales lead the way in opinion.

The core technology "BioResponse" consists of the "VideoScan" measuring system and test systems such as "Bead-Assay," "Cell-Assay," and "PCR-Array." Patents safeguard these innovations, showcasing economical components, top-notch lab tests, and versatility for various purposes. The BioResponse technology aims to establish a standard for diagnostic laboratories. Multi-parametric analysis of differential diagnosis of reactive and rheumatic arthropathies, infections, and other diseases has begun with the development of multiple possible diagnostic assays.

The primary target group for new products based on this cutting-edge technology is the medical professionals who work in hospitals and laboratory settings. Furthermore, applications for the life science sector and pharmaceutical analytics are being planned.

Der **Lausitzer Biotech e.V.** ist eine Initiative zur Förderung der regionalen Biotechnologie. Wir, das sind vor allem

engagierte Studenten/-innen und Mitarbeiter/-innen der Brandenburgischen Technischen Universität Cottbus-Senftenberg am Campus Senftenberg, machen uns bereits seit 2003 für die Biotechnologie in der Lausitz stark. Unser oberstes Ziel ist es, die Akzeptanz der Biotechnologie regional zu fördern. Dafür informieren wir nicht nur auf diversen Veranstaltungen über biotechnische Produkte, sondern weisen sowohl Schüler und Schülerinnen, als auch Studenten und Studentinnen der Biotechnologie Perspektiven für ihre Zukunft auf.

Unsere Ziele: Der Verein dient der Förderung der Biotechnologie in der Lausitz. Unser Ziel ist es, dass die Menschen in der Lausitz die Biotechnologie vor Ort und im Allgemeinen, d.h. im täglichen Leben besser wahrnehmen. Des Weiteren wollen wir die Biotechnologie-Studenten sowie den Studiengang Biotechnologie in Senftenberg durch gezielte Projekte unterstützen. Im Detail könnt ihr dazu unter Projekte Informationen finden.

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Poster Abstracts IBID 2023

10/10/23 - 10/19/23, BTU Cottbus - Senftenberg, Campus Senftenberg, Germany

(1) An unbiased approach of individual tissue-specific autoantibody identification using Immunoprecipitation coupled to Mass-Spectrometry (IP-MS) | Friederike A, Arlt, Elisa Sánchez, Sendín, Marieluise Kirchner, Mahoor Nasouti, Max Pelgrom De Haas, Philipp Mertins and Harald Prüss | Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin | friederike-antonia.arlt@charite.de

Background and aim: Autoreactive antibodies have gained increasing recognition in autoimmune diseases of the nervous system serving as disease drivers and / or biomarkers. Identification of novel autoantibodies therefore is crucial to optimize diagnostic work and therapy of these diseases as well as understanding their pathogenesis. Hence, we aimed to develop an unbiased strategy to identify patients' individual main autoantibodies directed against brain and nerve epitopes. Methods We used murine tissue-based assays to screen patients' sera and cerebrospinal fluids (CSFs) for autoreactive IgGs with known and unknown antibody targets. IgGs from autoreactive patients' samples were coupled to magnetic beads and used as a bait to pull down potential targets from homogenized brain and nerve tissue of wildtype mice. After precipitation and several washes to reduce unspecific binding, beads were subjected to on-bead tryptic digestion followed by mass spectrometry based proteomic analyses using liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). For antibody targets identification the fold change enrichment compared to a negative control or to all other pulldown samples, as well as the protein abundance was used. Antibody target validation was done via recombinant expression of the target protein in HEK-293 cells and neutralization with the respective antigen in tissue-based immunofluorescence assays. Results As proof of principle, we were able to identify Grin1 Caspr2, Trim46 and Nf-h as main targets of patients' sera or CSF with autoimmune encephalopathy. All four antigens showed highest enrichment and/or highest protein abundance in the respective samples and have been confirmed in cell-based assays. In addition, we identified two novel anti-neuronal antibody target in serum and CSF of two separate patients. Preabsorbance of the serum and CSF with the recombinant protein fully neutralized the signal of the tissue-based immunofluorescence. Conclusions Our IP-MS approach is suitable to identify the main autoantibody targets in patients' serum and CSF within murine tissue thereby providing an unbiased and scalable technique allowing for tissue-specific autoantibody determination.

(2) Differential Expression of MicroRNAs in Neurodegenerative Diseases | Christiane Geithe, Bo Zeng, Carsten Schmidt, Franziska Dinter, Dirk Roggenbuck, Werner Lehmann, Peter Schierack, Katja Hanack and Stefan Rödiger | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | azam@b-tu.de

Neurodegenerative diseases (NDs) occur due to brain or spinal cord neuron abnormalities that gradually lose their function and ultimately die. Pathological study of these tissues indicates the loss of synapses, misfolded protein tangles, and immune cell activation even in the initial stages of the disease, before the appearance of severe clinical symptoms. If NDs are detected early, targeted medications can slow disease progression. Treating early neuron damage and loss, or maintaining neuron functions, may be effective and prevent worse damage. Due to their complex pathophysiological characteristics and varied clinical symptoms, NDs lack sensitive and effective diagnostic methods. Moreover, no sensitive biomarkers are available to track ND progression, offer prognostic predictions, or measure therapeutic effectiveness. Recent studies indicate microRNAs (miRNAs) are potential biomarkers in diagnostics and therapy for NDs. MiRNAs are small, non-coding RNA molecules (about 18–25 nucleotides in length) that attach to mRNA and inhibit its expression. There are already over 1000 identified human miRNAs, and miRNAs regulate more than 50% of mammalian protein-coding genes. In specific diseases, miRNAs may be overexpressed or repressed, and the inhibition or replacement of miRNAs is a potential field of research for developing treatments. Research on miRNAs has primarily focused on two aspects: 1) miRNAs as possible disease biomarkers, and 2) miRNAs as a molecular target of disease therapies. We searched PubMed and found 350 articles. PubMed systematically searched for articles about miRNA levels in the blood, brain tissue, or cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) of ND patients vs. Healthy controls (HC). Eighty-three eligible studies were included for further analysis. We found that the most common microRNAs are let-7b, miR-124, miR-34a, and miR-29a. These microRNAs show up repeatedly

in scientific papers about different ND diseases. These miRNAs show the importance of miRNA biomarkers in clinical diagnostics and treatments of neurodegenerative diseases.

(3) Development of a penton gene-based isothermal recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) assay for rapid detection of the most common respiratory adenovirus subtypes | Benedikt Beilstein, Iris Bachmann, Frank T. Hufert, Gregory Dame | Institut Virologie und Mikrobiologie, MHB Theodor Fontante | benedikt.beilstein@mhb-fontane.de

Introduction: Infections with human respiratory adenoviruses (HAdV) can lead to dangerous acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) or trigger febrile seizures in children. Nucleic acid-based detection methods (e. g. PCR, RPA) commonly use the hexon gene as target, which shows a lack of homology in the multiple sequence alignment across different respiratory HAdV subtypes. The penton gene has been identified and shows highly conserved gene segments across these subtypes. The aim was to develop a pan-respiratory assay of the most common respiratory HAdV subtypes (HAdV-B7, -B14, -E4, -C2) using PCR and RPA as an isothermal and bioanalytical tool for rapid detection. Material & Methods: Gene segments of the common respiratory HAdV subtypes were aligned to find homologous sequences. Primers and probes for PCR and RPA were designed using bioinformatic tools. To determine the analytical sensitivity of both amplification systems, molecular DNA standards of the gene target were prepared and tested in a decadic dilution series. A Panel of 22 different respiratory viruses were used to test analytical specificity of the RPA assay. To demonstrate successful application in clinical samples, nasopharyngeal swab samples from children with respiratory symptoms were screened for HAdV using the novel PCR and RPA assays. Results: A region of the penton gene (Gene Bank: JX423383.1: 15278-15507 bp) showed the highest homology of about 86 % (197/230 bp) across all respiratory subtypes. A PCR- based primer probe system for the detection of HAdV subtypes B and E was established, as well as a separate PCR-based primer probe system for the detection of HAdV subtype C. The PCR systems show high sensitivity ranging from 3.66 to 5.32 molecular standard copies. For RPA, we were able to create one equal pan-probe to cover all relevant HAdV subtypes in a one-tube assay. Pan-RPA showed sensitivities from 14.2 to 137 molecular standard copies across the different HAdV subtypes. RT-RPA showed no cross-reactivity with other DNA or RNA viruses tested in fifteen cases (excluded adenoviruses). Four RNA samples showed indistinct results. Out of 253 clinical specimens, eight samples were tested positive for HAdV using our PCR and seven were confirmed positive using the pan-respiratory RPA assay. Conclusion: In contrast to the frequently used hexon gene-based nucleic amplification assays, we were able to detect the most common respiratory HAdV subtypes (B7, B14, E4, C2) using one-tube RPA approach. Our novel pan-respiratory RPA assay with one fluorescent pan-probe offers the possibility of rapid, isothermal and real-time detection of mainly respiratory HAdV subtypes (B7, B14, E4, C2).

(4) Sustainable Design of Online Biosensors | Mario Birkholz and Martin Kögler | IHP - Leibniz-Institut für innovative Mikroelektronik | birkholz@ihp-microelectronics.com

The sector of information and communication technology (ICT) has seen a steady increase in global energy consumption, accounting for 5-8% of global electricity consumption in 2020 and for 3% of all greenhouse gas emissions [1]. In particular, the evolving Internet-of-Things (IoT) will become a major consumer with a projected increase from 15e9 devices in 2015 to 75e9 in 2025. Biosensors for medical monitoring or fitness trackers are mostly designed as IoT devices and the question is how to design them so that their use will not neutralize sustainability efforts. 1. The sustainability of biosensor systems under development can be assessed on the basis of the 17 UN Sustainability Goals (SDG). 2. Solutions developed by the smartphone manufacturer Fairphone and others may be used for material selection and sustainable production processes of biosensor systems. 3. MICS [2] or BTLE [3] are suitable for energy-saving and harvesting for real-time data transmission of online biosensors. 4 Medical monitoring of patients is undergoing a transition from external wearables such as wrist- and skinpatches, rings, chest straps, headbands, etc. to semi-implants or implant-table biosensors. While the first are used to monitor bodily functions, the latter apply to biochemical analytes and biomarkers in the body. 5. Wearable and biosensor users are currently confronted with an unsustainable structure of the Internet. An oligopoly of a few large platforms dominates almost all areas via operating systems for smartphones (Google's Android, Apple's iOS) or computers (Microsoft Windows) and via "social" media (Twitter's microblogger, Meta's Instagram, Facebook and WhatsApp, and Google's YouTube). 6. Information is tapped from users via non-transparent spying techniques in order to derive personality profiles for commercial and political advertising campaigns [4]. 7. Health data are subject to special protection according to Art. 9 of the European GDPR. 8. Given the current state of the internet, it

may not be expected that this protection can be guaranteed if systems or services are used from the above-mentioned oligopoly. 9. Data storage for online biosensor should be designed in edge mode, so that the data is stored at the user's site and transferred to other entities such as the treating physician only with the user's explicit consent. 10. Tools and apps developed by the FOSS community (free-and-open-source software) should best be used for data processing. A good example is the DRIP app for cycle monitoring, whose basic principles may be applied to biosensors for other parameters. A CO₂ footprint minimizing design of online biosensors should always be considered in order to meet SDG 7 and 13. Furthermore, the current structure of the Internet with a few Big-Data monopolists is highly unsustainable. The profits from the personal data obtained exceed the budgets of most states on earth, which is incompatible with SDG 10 that calls for reducing income inequalities within and among countries. Given the current situation, biosensor data should be stored only locally. References [1] C. Freitag et al., doi: 10.1016/j.patter.2021.100340. [2] T. Basmer et al., doi: 10.1109/IMWS-BIO.2013.6756194 [3] D. Nguyen et al., doi: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3164157. [4] S. Zuboff, *The age of surveillance capitalism: the fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. London: Profile books, 2019.

(5) ConsensusPrime - a bioinformatic pipeline for ideal consensus primer design | Maximilian Collatz, Sascha D, Braun, Stefan Monecke and Ralf Ehrlich | Leibniz-IPHT Jena | Maximilian.Collatz@leibniz-ipht.de

High quality oligonucleotides for molecular amplification and detection procedures of diverse target sequences depend on sequence homology. The processing of input sequences and the identification of homogeneous regions in alignments can be done manually only if alignments are small and if they contain sequences of high similarity. For large and inhomogeneous alignments, the process of finding the best regions needs to be automated. The ConsensusPrime pipeline was developed sort out redundant and technical interfering data in multiple sequence alignments and detect the most homolog regions from multiple sequences. It automates the prediction of optimal consensus primers for molecular analytical and sequence-based procedures/assays. ConsensusPrime is a fast and easy to use pipeline for predicting optimal consensus primers that is executable on local systems without depending on external resources and web-services. An implementation in a Docker image ensures platform-independent executability and installability despite the combination of multiple programs. The source code and installation instructions are publicly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/mcollatz/ConsensusPrime>).

(6) Microbeads for Immobilisation of Amphiphilic Biomarkers | Franziska Dinter, Thomas Thiele, Uwe Schedler, Christoph Jurischka, Werner Lehmann, Peter Schierack and Stefan Rödiger | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | franziska.dinter@b-tu.de

Introduction: Lipids and amphiphilic molecules are ubiquitous and play a central role in the human body. Lipid alterations occur in diseases such as cardiovascular disease [1], cancer and autoimmune diseases. Therefore, detection systems for lipids and amphiphilic molecules are needed. Microbeads are powerful for simultaneous quantitative multiplex detection of different lipophilic biomarkers [2]. Results and Discussion: Fluorescence-encoded and solvent-resistant microbeads for immobilising amphiphilic molecules did not exist until now. We succeeded in producing such microbeads. By passive adsorption, the phospholipids A, B and C could be bound to the microbead surfaces. Directional binding of these was confirmed by enzymatic reaction. Microbeads with a hydrophilic surface bind phospholipids non-directionally and are no longer re-actively accessible. Thus, a hydrophobic microbead surface is mandatory. Exemplary for the application of this microbeads, anti-IgG cardiolipin antibodies were detected with the hydrophobic microbeads from human serum. Conclusions: With the newly developed hydrophobic, dual-encoded and solvent-resistant microbeads, it is possible to bind amphiphilic biomolecules to the microbead surfaces in a directed manner. One application of the platform is the detection of anti-phospholipid antibodies from human serum. References 1. Dinter, F.; Burdukiewicz, M.; Schierack, P.; Lehmann, W.; Nestler, J.; Dame, G.; Rödiger, S., *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00216-019-02199-x 2. Dinter, F.; Thiele, T.; Schedler, U.; Lehmann, W.; Schierack, P.; Rödiger, S., *bioRxiv* 2023, doi: 10.1101/2023.01.10.523433

(7) Scaffold-free differentiation of bone cells from different isolation techniques | Annemarie Ecke, Heiko Richter and Ursula Anderer | Department of Cell Biology and Tissue Engineering, BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | annemarie.ecke@b-tu.de

Introduction: The standard isolation of bone cells capable of bone formation is very tedious taking up to eight weeks for the initial culture to reach confluence. Other isolation protocols use enzymatic digestion of

the tissues; however, so far the resulting cells have not been compared to the standard isolation regarding their capability of bone formation. Furthermore, bone formation in vitro is often realised in 3D by using scaffolds. Hence, the aim of this study was to compare the maturation of scaffold-free microtissues of bone cells from different isolation techniques. Methods: Human primary bone cells were isolated from knee joints of two donors. The bone parts were cut into pieces and one portion subjected to the standard isolation protocol (explants). The resulting cell fraction was designated as ExB. The other portion of bone pieces was exposed to a two-step collagenase digestion and the cells designated as OsB (osteoblastic cells). Both cell fractions were expanded in monolayer culture. Prior to analyses or 3D culture, half of the cells were treated with bone differentiation factors (predifferentiation) for four days. Monolayer cells were analysed regarding their expression of bone-specific markers via immunocytochemistry. Scaffold-free microtissues were generated using cell-repellent plates. After eight weeks, the macroscopic appearance and size was assessed. The differentiation degree of bone-like microtissues was evaluated via histology. Results: The initial culture of OsB took half the time to reach confluence as ExB. The morphology and expression of bone-specific markers of both cell fractions was similar. The expression of alkaline phosphatase was elevated in cells subjected to predifferentiation. Microtissues of both cell fractions displayed similar properties: those generated from predifferentiated cells were on average 60 % bigger and white in colour. Only microtissues generated from predifferentiated cells displayed a mineralized matrix evidenced by von Kossa staining. Fast Green staining showed the presence of collagen type I. As seen in monolayer, microtissues from predifferentiated cells showed elevated alkaline phosphatase expression. Discussion: This study showed that both isolation techniques resulted in cells of similar morphology, gene expression and behaviour. Furthermore, the results indicate that the predifferentiation of the cells prior to microtissue formation is indispensable for successful bone formation in vitro.

(8) TumOC – a tumour organoid-on-chip device for real-time measurements of drug treatment impact | Marie Flechner, Jürgen Loskutov, Ulrike Pfohl, Katja Osman, Madeleine Nadolny, Christian RA Regenbrecht, Lena Wedeken and Katja Uhlig | Fraunhofer IZI-BB | Marie.flechner@izi-bb.fraunhofer.de

Colorectal carcinomas (CRC) are one of the most common malignant tumours and are often incurable due to their heterogeneity and high probability of metastasis. Therefore, improved therapies are needed, which consequently have to pass through the different phases of drug development. Physiologically relevant in-vitro tumour models increase the success rate of new pharmaceuticals, reduce the number of animal testing and result finally in improved therapies for cancer patients. In recent years, 3D cell cultures were established as relevant preclinical cancer models suitable for high-throughput screening. However, their ability to represent physiological processes can still be significantly improved. Here, we are developing a tumour organoid-on-chip device (TumOC) by combining three recent technological advances: We integrated i) patient-derived 3D cell cultures (organoids) from colorectal carcinomas that recapitulate the architecture and heterogeneity of the original tumour, ii) oxygen microsensor particles to assess cell viability in real time and iii) microfluidic perfusion for defined exposure of cytostatic drugs. Parameters of the seeding protocol (organoid number and size) and the perfusion rate were optimised so that differences in cell respiration can be detected and evaluated. Subsequently we investigated CRC tumour organoids with different cytostatic drug sensitivities in TumOC and compared the kinetic measurements with the endpoint measurements performed with an ATP assay. In addition, the ability to mimic plasma concentration profiles of the patient's medications was integrated into TumOC. Our TumOC, with its ability to recapitulate tumour heterogeneity in combination with dynamic treatments and real-time assessment of cell viability, is an in vitro tumour model that offers an impressive opportunity to test and consequently predict the efficacy of cancer therapies pre-therapeutically.

(9) Generation of camelid single domain antibodies originated from a naïve or immunized camelid library to design a new innovative hydrogel-based assay for analysis of neurodegenerative biomarkers | Bianca Hartmann, Markus Goethel, Sophia Michelchen, Katja Hanack, | new/era/mabs GmbH, Potsdam, Germany, University of Potsdam, Germany | contact@neweramabs.com

Single domain antibodies, known as VHHs, derived from camelids, have emerged as potent tools in biotechnology due to their ability to selectively bind antigens using a single heavy chain variable domain. These VHHs exhibit exceptional stability, withstanding high temperatures, pH fluctuations, and detergent exposure, setting them apart from conventional murine or human antibodies. In the context of the NeuroMiR project, the Immunotechnology department at the University of Potsdam focuses on generating VHHs tailored to bind specific neurodegenerative biomarkers, forming precise antibody-antigen complexes. Concurrently, the

biotechnology company new/era/mabs GmbH is dedicated to identifying VHHs capable of binding DNA:RNA hybrid complexes within a hydrogel-based assay. To achieve this, a random DNA:RNA hybrid complex was synthesized and immobilized, paving the way for the detection of microRNAs that function as neurodegenerative biomarkers in blood samples. Employing phage display technology, the Immunotechnology team has successfully isolated specific monoclonal VHHs against neurodegenerative markers like phosphorylated tau protein (pTau217). Multiple VHHs targeting other relevant biomarkers have also been generated. This study represents a significant advancement in harnessing VHHs' unique attributes for cutting-edge biotechnological applications in the realm of neurodegenerative disease diagnosis.

(10) Comparison of total DNA extraction methods for rapid detection of carbapenemase-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* | Cecilia Heller, Iris Bachmann, Frank T Hufert and Gregory Dame | Medizinische Hochschule Brandenburg | cecilia.heller@mhb-fontane.de

Introduction: Rapid and accurate detection of antibiotic resistance is decisive for infection control and targeted antibiotic therapy. For nucleic acid-based detection, the quality and quantity of DNA is crucially affected by the choice of nucleic acid purification method. Challenges for DNA extraction arises from the potential presence of carbapenemase genes in genome and/or large plasmids (larger than 70 kb), where standard extractions might fail. Additionally, when used in point-of-care (POC) settings, like with clinical specimens such as rectal swabs, target cell abundance is limited, and potential inhibition due to faecal contamination must be considered. Material and Methods: To identify optimal extraction efficiencies, we investigated extracted total DNA from *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains containing beta-lactamase (bla) genes blaOXA-48, blaNDM-1, blaKPC-2, and blaVIM-1. We compared two gold standard methods QIAamp Fast DNA Stool Mini Kit (QIAGEN) and NucleoSpin® DNA Stool Kit (MACHEREY-NAGEL) with the POC capable systems EchoLUTION Buccal Swab DNA Kit (BioEcho), EchoLUTION Viral RNA/DNA Swab Kit Plus (BioEcho), Quick Extract™ (Lucigen) and thermal lysis (colony PCR and heat block). Each carbapenemase gene was cloned and calibration standard lines were generated. To simulate bacterial load of a rectal swab according Chanderraj et al. and Warnke et al., we added an uniform amount of 105 CFU / 200 µL to each extraction, controlled by OD600 measurements and drop plate method. To determine the limits of detection in a subsequent qPCR, in each extraction system, an amount of CFUs from 104 - 101 CFUs / 200 µL of a representative *K. pneumoniae* strain was applied. Results: Adding 200 µL of 5 · 105 CFU / mL each, the extraction methods yielded, annexed to the calibration line, for both gold standard kits a range from 1 to maximum 100 copy numbers / µL, for both variations of thermal lysis a maximum of 2000 copy numbers / µL, for BioEcho kits 200 to maximum 2000 copy numbers / µL and for QuickExtract™ (Lucigen) up to 104 copies / µL. By reduction of 104 – 101 CFUs, gold standard kits showed a detection limit of 105 introduced CFUs, the other methods were still amplifiable with 104 CFU inserted. Conclusion: We demonstrated that the concentration of 105 CFU / 200 µL was close to the detection limit and gold standard kits were the least sensitive: Among the column-based applications, the BioEcho kits yielded the highest copy numbers (factor 10 to 200 compared to gold standard kits), while QuickExtract™ (Lucigen) yielded highest among applications without columns (factor 10) and in the overall result. These rapid and efficient extraction methods can extract total DNA from small quantities of bacteria typically found on rectal swabs and could prove valuable for POC applications in conjunction with rapid detection techniques like recombinase polymerase amplification.

(11) An efficient and scalable platform for the production of immunogenic SARS-CoV-2 Virus-Like Particles (VLP) from a mammalian suspension cell line: Application as universal display system for membrane bound antigens | Stefan Hirschberg | Charité -Universitätsmedizin Berlin | stefan.hirschberg@charite.de

The aim of this study was to generate an efficient production system for SARS-CoV-2 VLPs. The SARS-CoV-2 N-, M-, and E-protein genes were integrated into the genome of suspension adapted HEK293 cells (VLP_MEN). Subsequently, this cell line was further modified for the constitutive expression of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. The resulting cell line (VLP_SMEN) released SARS-CoV-2 VLP upon exposure to doxycycline. Purified VLPs were analyzed by western blot, mass spectrometry, ELISA, and nanoparticle tracking analysis and visualized by electron microscopy. The VLPs contained all four structural proteins, are within the size range of authentic SARS-CoV-2 virus particles and reacted strongly and specifically with immunoserum from naturally-infected individuals. Mice immunized with VLPs developed neutralizing antibodies against lentiviruses pseudotyped with the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. The flexibility of the VLP-production platform was demonstrated by the rapid switch of the spike protein to a new variant of concern

(BA.1/Omicron). Furthermore, we explored the VLP production system to express tumor markers, GPCRs and ion-channels/transporters on the membrane of VLPs. These chimeric VLPs (cVLPs) display the target surface molecules in their native conformation. This cell line is suitable as a universal antigen display system for immunization/vaccination as well as for the screening of drug and antibody candidates.

(12) Exploration of membranes for fluorescence-based analysis of biological specimens. | Christoph Jurischka, Franziska Dinter, Katharina Sydow, Katharina Schaufler, Marc Wegmann, Dirk Roggenbuck, Peter Schierack and Stefan Rödiger | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | christoph.jurischka@b-tu.de

Fluorescence-based analytical methods are frequently used for the qualitative and quantitative detection of microorganisms or biomolecules from patient or environmental samples. Such methods are very sensitive and specific, but require analysis surfaces with low autofluorescence, low abiotic properties and high binding capacity for reproducible and reliable results. Particularly in the case of small quantities of analytes, these must first be concentrated. For this type of investigation, filters and membranes are useful on which the analytes can be well immobilized, stained and optically analyzed. We compared different filter and membrane materials (nitrocellulose, polyethersulfone, polyvinylidene fluoride, polyethylene terephthalate, polycarbonate). The autofluorescence of the materials was analyzed by fluorescence spectrometry and the surface was examined by different microscopic techniques (Epifluorescence, Laser Scanning, Atomic Force Microscopy). The adhesion and location of microorganisms on the surfaces were analyzed by fluorescence microscopy after nonspecific (nucleic acid dyes) and specific (fluorescent probes hybridization) staining, and additionally the growth on them was studied. For this purpose, the materials were dealt with 3D-printed holders and integrated in (micro-) fluidic devices. We were able to find a suitable planar membrane with low background fluorescence and good binding properties, which is highly applicable for fluorescence-based bioanalytical methods. Conclusions Membranes are used in a wide range of bioanalytical applications, but are not only useful for separating or concentrating substances. The direct analysis of samples on them is also advantageous and simplifies, for example, the diagnosis of pathogens that are difficult to cultivate. The membranes described can be used both on a larger scale, but can just as easily be incorporated into small instruments such as microfluidic chips, which can be automatically evaluated with fluorescence microscopy systems.

(13) Digital and multiplex detection of microRNAs for early cancer diagnosis | Coline Kieffer, Yannick Rondelez and Guillaume Gines | ESPCI-Paris, PSL University | coline.kieffer@espci.fr

MicroRNAs are short non-coding RNAs (~ 20 nt) dysregulated in a number of pathologies, including cancers and neurodegenerative diseases. Since they are released in a stable form in the bloodstream, miRNAs are attractive biomarkers for the development of liquid biopsies. Their detection is however challenging, requiring sensitivity, specificity, quantitativity and a high multiplex ability. We designed a low- background enzymatic amplification machinery enabling the sensitive detection of miRNAs. Coupling this approach with a microbead-based format and droplet microfluidics, we developed a multiplex digital miRNA detection method. This technique shows great potential for the early and non-invasive cancer diagnosis and prognosis by molecular profiling.

(14) FLASHlab@PITZ — R&D platform for electron UHDR and FLASH radiation biology at PITZ, DESY | Y. Komar, A. Grebinyk, F. Stephan, M. Fröhme, N. Aftab, Z. Amirkhanyan, A. Asoyan, P. Boompornprasert, H. Davtyan, D. Dmytriiev, P. Borchert, G. Georgiev, C. M. Groß, A. Hoffmann, M. Krasilnikov, X. Li, M. Liebe, G. Loisch, Z. Lotfi, A. Oppelt, A. Radioivoych, C. Richard, F. Riemer, G. Vashchenko, D. Villani | Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) | yulia.komar@desy.de

Radiation treatment with ultra-high dose rate (UHDR) in short time intervals lead to considerably lower toxicity in the healthy tissue keeping therapeutic response of the tumor. The 22 MeV electron beam which is available at the Photo Injector Test facility at DESY in Zeuthen (PITZ) will deliver radiation at both UHDR up to 1014 Gy/s and conventional low dose rate used in the clinical radiation therapy. Cancer radiation treatment mainly acts by cell death induction and proliferation inhibition in tumor tissue. Ionizing irradiation in water causes its radiolysis and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation. The indirect and direct interaction of ionizing radiation with DNA leads to its damage that results in cell proliferation inhibition and induction of cell death. FLASHlab@PITZ works together with the Technical University of Applied Sciences Wildau as a partner in close vicinity for the chemical and biological resources. Our aim is to provide the radiation oncology community with an in vitro and in vivo infrastructure for systematic investigation of electron radiation at an extremely wide dose rate range from conventional to UHDR. The startup FLASHlab@PITZ-beamline consists of a 60 dipole, BPMs, ICT, Faraday cup, screen station, titanium window, experimental area and one more

screen and Faraday cup in air. In first in vitro studies the irradiation is being performed with a 18 MeV PITZ electron beam at doses up to 150 Gy and dose rates of 0.05 Gy/s for conventional and 105-106 Gy/s for UHDR at 21% O₂. The initial chemical (ROS), biochemical (DNA plasmid damage) and biological (cell proliferation) in vitro experiments with FLASHlab@PITZ beam irradiation, as well as the status of building an in vivo research infrastructure at PITZ will be overviewed with this contribution. The first studies at FLASHlab@PITZ focused on the chemical, biochemical and biological effects in vitro of electron radiation that opened up biological research at PITZ and its perspective for further development of UHDR radiation therapy.

(15) Over-expression of LEDGF/p75/DSF70 in HEp-2 cells enhances autoimmune IgG response in patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) - a novel diagnostic approach with therapeutic consequences? | Victoria Liedtke, Laura Rose, Rico Hiemann, Abdullah Nasser, Stefan Rödiger, Alena Bonaventura, Laura Winkler, Mandy Sowa, Michael Stöckle, Peter Schierack, Kerstin Junker and Dirk Roggenbuck | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | victoria.liedtke@b-tu.de

Benign prostate hyperplasia (BPH) is an enlargement of the prostate with a prevalence of 50% to 75% in men 50 years of age and older. The pathophysiology of BPH is not yet fully elucidated, but for almost 100 years, the possibility of autoimmune disease has always played a role. Therefore, autoantibody (autoAb) testing could aid in the diagnosis of BPH patients profiting from a corresponding immunosuppressive therapy by TNFalpha antagonists. Lens epithelium-derived growth factor-splice variant of 75kDa (LEDGF/p75), also known as DFS70, is an autoantigen which is over-expressed in solid tumors and acts as a stress-related transcriptional co-activator. Thus, we generated CRISPR/Cas9 modified HEp-2 LEDGF knock-out (KO) and HEp-2 LEDGF/p75 over-expressing (OE) cells and examined IgG autoantibody reactivity to LEDGF/p75 in patients with prostate cancer (PCa, n=89), bladder cancer (BCa, n=116), benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH, n=103), and blood donors (BD, n=60) by indirect immunofluorescence assay (IFA). Surprisingly, we could not detect elevated binding of autoAbs against LEDGF/p75 in cancer patients, but an unexpectedly significantly increased autoAb reactivity to LEDGF/p75 OE cells in about 50% of patients with BPH. Furthermore, a line immunoassay enabling the detection of 18 different autoAbs revealed a significantly increased occurrence of anti-dsDNA autoAbs in 34% of BPH patients in contrast to tumor patients and BD. We could confirm this finding by anti-mitochondrial (mDNA) autoAb detection with the Crithidia luciliae immunofluorescence test that also showed a significantly higher prevalence (34%) of anti-mDNA autoAbs in BPH. In summary, our study provided further evidence for the occurrence of autoimmune responses in BPH. Furthermore, LEDGF/p75 over-expression renders HEp-2 cells more autoantigenic and an ideal target for autoAb analysis in BPH with a potential therapy consequence.

(16) Aptamers Targeting Human Urokinase for Therapeutic and Diagnostic Applications | Nico Dreymann, Julia Wuensche, Wiebke Sabrowski, Jennifer Danso, Anja Moeller, Denise Czepluch, Dana Vu Van, Susanne Fuessel and Marcus M. Menger | Fraunhofer Institute for Cell Therapy and Immunology, Branch Bioanalytics and Bioprocesses (IZI-BB) | marcus.menger@izi-bb.fraunhofer.de

Early cancer detection and therapy are one of the most important tasks of today's medicine as the number of cancer incidences is increasing, and according to the World Health Organization (WHO), will rise rapidly in the next years. Many studies have focused on the molecular level of tumor development, using aberrant expression of various proteins as potential targets for cancer therapy or biomarkers for cancer diagnosis.

(17) 3D-printed microfluidic chip system with integrated passive mixing structures | Christian Neubert, Tim L. Brauckhoff, Frank T. Hufert and Gregory Dame | Medizinische Hochschule Brandenburg Theodor Fontane, Institut für Mikrobiologie und Virologie | christian.neubert@mhb-fontane.de

Introduction: Integration of the isothermal recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) assay into a microfluidic system is challenging because introduced reagents have different viscosities and a mixing step (RPA) is mandatory. 3D printing offers great potential for rapid and cost-effective fabrication of microfluidic Lab-on-a-chip LOC systems with integrated mixing structures. Three mixing structures - staggered herringbone mixer (SHM), Tesla structure and split-and-recombine mixer (SAR) - were 3D printed and the performance were characterised with two different poorly miscible dye solutions. In addition to the investigations of the mixed structures, the "pure" diffusion was investigated as a negative control (diffusion control). M&M: For design of the constructs SolidWorks was used and for realisation Digital Light Processing (DLP) printer (W2P, Austria). For evaluation the mixing efficiency, Coomassie and Congo red solutions were injected into two separate inlets and merged into one channel. A phaseguide was integrated so that the fluids could enter the

mixing channel more controlled at the same time and without bubbles. The mixing rate was investigated with different flow rates from 0.5 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ to 100 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. The mixing efficiency was evaluated with an adapted equation concerning different R-packages for standard deviation and linear regression. Results: At low flow rates of 0.5 - 1 l/min , the fluids (dye solutions) show mixing efficiencies of more than 80 % in all structures as well as in the controls, indicating diffusion-driven mixing. The control and SAR structures results show lower efficiencies (40%) at higher flow rates from 2 μl to 100 μl , the in the. The Tesla structure shows a mixing efficiency of > 90% until a flow rate of 40 l/min , but above 40 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ the efficiency of the Tesla structure drops sharply. The SHM structure shows a high mixing efficiency of more 90 % in all measured flow rates 0.5 l/min to 100 l/min , Conclusion: Tesla and SHM mixing structures would be interesting for microfluidic lab-on-a-chip systems, but the Tesla structure shows at higher flow rates reduced efficiencies. The Staggered Herringbone Mixer structure seems almost independent from different flowrates. For integration of RPA in a LOC system, SHM structure would be suitable.

(18) Label-free bioanalytical platform based on LQ-Whispering Gallery Modes | Mateusz Olszyna, Götz Dähne, Lars Dähne | SurfRay Nanotec GmbH | m.olszyna@surflay.com

The success in preparing monodisperse fluorescent microparticles with almost ideal spherical shapes during the last 20 years allowed the observation of so-called Whispering Gallery Modes (WGM) after the excitation of the particles by light. Therefore, several publications and patents were published claiming the usage of such particles for the label-free detection of biomolecules like DNA, RNA, or proteins by specific interaction with the functionalized particles surface. Due to changes in the surface refractive index and size by adsorption of such molecules, the WGM resonance shift is very sensitive, allowing a quantitative analysis of the molecules. The advantage of the analytical method is the independence of a pre-modification of the bio-molecules with fluorescent dyes or other markers. In this work, we demonstrate the label-free bioanalytical sensing platform based on the excitation of LQ-WGM resonance in spherical, micrometer-sized biosensors, designed for real-time monitoring of specific interactions of (bio)molecules.

(19) The antibacterial active agent triclosan and its substitute chlorhexidine alter the immune response of monocytes and THP-1 macrophages | Stefanie Raps, Laura Bahr, Isabel Karkossa, Manuela Rossol, Martin von Bergen and Kristin Schubert | Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH – UFZ | stefanie.raps@ufz.de

Resulting from the restriction of the bacteriocidal Triclosan (TCS) by regulatory agencies in Europe and the US, substitutes for TCS are emerging. While TCS has recently been shown to alter immune metabolism and activate the NLRP3 inflammasome by releasing IL-1 in human macrophages, knowledge about its alternatives is scarce. Therefore, we aim to elucidate the effects of TCS and its substitutes in human macrophages using untargeted proteomics. To examine the modes of action of the antimicrobials, THP-1 cells were stimulated with LPS to mimic an acute infection, and the TCS or its alternatives, including cetylpyridinium chloride, benzalkonium chloride, benzethonium chloride, chloroxylenol and chlorhexidine (CHX). An ELISA study unravelled the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF and IL-1 in TCS-treated cells, suggesting inflammasome activation, which was confirmed with MCC950 experiments, an NLRP3-inhibitor. The alternative CHX completely abolished cytokine release, while the other substitutes reduced the release of TNF and IL-1. A reduction of IL-6 was determined among all treatments. An untargeted LC-MS/MS-based proteomics approach was used to decipher the underlying molecular process. After 24 hours of treatment, TCS and its substitute CHX showed the strongest response on protein and pathway levels. Due to oxidative stress conditions, both antimicrobials inhibited signalling pathways related to metabolism, like glycolysis, TCA cycle and oxidative phosphorylation. In CHX-treated cells, translation was arrested, and the formation of stress granules was determined using fluorescence microscopy as well as podosome formation, resulting in ECM degradation. These findings were underpinned by a networked-based key driver analysis (WGCNA), where small and large ribosomal proteins and proteins related to actin cytoskeleton signalling were unrevealed as putative key drivers for CHX. The obtained results highlight critical processes in the immune response of macrophages under TCS and substitute exposure, especially CHX, which are indispensable for hazard assessment in immunotoxicity, thereby supporting the minimisation of adverse effects.

(20) Cell counts, genome copy numbers or estimated genome equivalents – Introducing a new nanoreactor-based digital PCR for detection and absolute quantification of bacterial pathogens | Martin Reinicke, Celia Diezel, Sascha D, Braun, Ines Engelmann, Theresa Liebe and Ralf Ehrlich | Leibniz-IPHT Jena | Martin.Reinicke@leibniz-ipht.de

Introduction: The basis for determining the limit of detection (LOD) of different molecular diagnostic methods is the absolute quantification of bacteria and followed by a theoretical calculation of their genome equivalents (GE). This is usually done either by cultivation and subsequent cell counting or by molecular methods such as quantitative or digital PCR. Direct quantification by cultivation or cell counting is affected by a possible presence of cell conglomerates or of dead cells. Molecular methods usually calculate genome equivalents based on DNA concentration and genome size or determine the copy number of genetic markers. For this study, the correlations between cell numbers during different growth phases and genome copies in *E. coli* were investigated using a new bead-based digital PCR. **Methods:** Growth kinetics was analysed using the *E. coli* strain Nissle 1917. Cell numbers were determined by OD600, plating and most probable number (MPN) of samples from different (lag, log and stationary) phases. To quantify genome copies, DNA was isolated by bead beating without further purification and directly bound to nanoreactor beads out of crude extract. The chromosomal species marker *gad* (glutamate decarboxylase gene) was used in a digital PCR using nanoreactor beads. **Results:** Cell number determination from plating and estimation by MPN gave equivalent results. During the growth experiment, samples were taken from the culture at the lag phase, the exponential phase and the stationary phase for the isolation of genomic DNA. Based on the assumption that each cell contains at least one and two complete genomes, a theoretical number of GEs was calculated by multiplying the number of cells by 1.5. Preliminary analysis of the lag phase sample showed a 10-fold higher number of genomic copies per microlitre than the absolute number of cells in the sample and more than 6-fold higher than the calculated GEs. **Discussion:** The study shows the relationship between cell number and genome copies and the influence of growth phases. The described method allows an absolute quantification of genome copies in a sample due to the high number of nanoreactor beads. The binding of DNA without any purification step out of a lysed sample reduces the bias of sample preparation in comparison to column-based systems. The results confirm the occurrence of more than one genome copy per cell. For DNA-based diagnostic tests, this method allow a more accurate LOD calculation in terms of copy number and ultimately pathogen number.

(21) A Multiplex Microchamber Diffusion Assay for the Antibody-based Detection of microRNAs on Randomly Ordered Microbeads | Christiane Geithe, Bo Zeng, Carsten Schmidt, Franziska Dinter, Dirk Roggenbuck, Werner Lehmann, Peter Schierack, Katja Hanack and Stefan Rödiger | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | stefan.roediger@b-tu.de

Background: MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small, conserved, noncoding RNAs regulating gene expression that functions in RNA silencing and post-transcriptional regulation of gene expression. Altered miRNA profiles have been implicated in many human diseases, and due to their circulating abilities, they have excited great interest in their use as clinical biomarkers. The development of innovative methods for miRNA detection has become of high scientific and clinical interest. **Methods:** We developed a diffusion-driven microbead assay and combined it with an antibody-based miRNA detection. The diffusion process was carried out in two different approaches a) co-diffusion of miRNA and antibodies (termed diffusion approach I, DAI) and b) diffusion of miRNA in an antibody-saturated environment (DAII). In both approaches, neutravidin-coated microbeads were loaded with specific biotinylated DNA capture probes, which targets either miR-21-5p, miR-30a-3p or miR-93-5p. The miRNAs were time- and dose-dependently detected in a diffusion microchamber by primary anti-DNA:RNA hybrid and fluorescence-labeled secondary antibodies using our in-house developed inverse fluorescence microscope imaging platform VideoScan. **Results:** Our assay offers the advantage that several target molecules can be detected simultaneously and in real-time in one reaction environment (multiplex), without any amplification steps. We recorded the diffusion process over a period of 24 h and found that the reaction was almost completed after 2 h. The specificity of the assay was 96.7 % for DAI and 92.3 % for DAII. The detection limits were in a concentration range of 0.03-0.43 nM for DAI and 0.14-1.09 nM for DAII, depending on the miRNA. **Conclusion:** The miRNAs are successively exposed to the capture probe-loaded randomly ordered microbeads (p value of CSR 0.23-0.96), which leads to microbeads that become saturated with the target molecules first in front rows. Non-bonded miRNAs continue to diffuse further and can therefore subsequently bind to the microbeads with free binding sites. Our detection principle differs from other microbead assays, in which all microbeads are simultaneously mixed with the sample solution, so that all target molecules bind equally distributed to the microbeads, resulting in an averaged signal intensity.

(22) Scalable Manufacturing of Electro-Optical Glass Chips for Integrated Sensing | H, Al,Shami, J, Kocis, O, Sperling, T, Chojne, J, Schwietering, and H, Schröder | Fraunhofer IZM | julian.schwietering@izm.fraunhofer.de

Fraunhofer IZM has developed a glass platform that can be electrically and optically functionalized for the use in sensing applications. Electrical circuits and electrodes made of metal can now be incorporated in, or on the glass surface. Optical waveguides are integrated in the glass and can be brought to the surface both by an ion-exchange process. These waveguides are transparent over a wide optical range (600 to 1600 nm) and can be structured to integrate optical functions such as ring resonators, beam splitters, Mach-Zehnder interferometers and more. The glass can also be structured with laser technologies to realize microfluidic channels. As such, multiple sensing principles are made possible including conductivity, evanescent field sensing, absorption, plasmonic sensing (SPR), refractometric measurements among others. All processes are developed on large formatted panels, so more than e.g. 100 glass chips can be fabricated on one glass substrate.

(23) Design and generation of antibody-drug conjugates containing non-canonical amino acids by using cell-free and cell-based systems | Nathanaël Rakotoarino, Yan Dyck, Jeffrey L. Schloßhauer, Simon K, Krebs, Franziska Ramm, Dana Wenzel, Miriam, Kouso Assi, Anne Zemella, Maria K, Parr and Marlitt Stech | Fraunhofer Institute for Cell Therapy and Immunology (IZI) Branch Bioanalytics and Bioprocesses (IZI-BB) | marlitt.stech@izi-bb.fraunhofer.de

The concept of antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs) is theoretically simple, but it is difficult to combine their components into an optimized and functional therapeutic agent. With most conjugation technologies, the choice of the conjugation site is limited, or pre-functionalization of the conjugation site is required. This leads to limited possibilities of optimization and extensive downstream processes, respectively. Against this background, we develop biochemical tools for the site-specific modification of antibodies using the amber suppression technology. We use two different approaches: Mammalian cell-based as well as novel mammalian cell-free systems. Here we demonstrate the synthesis of “ready-to-conjugate” antibodies containing site-specifically introduced 2-azidoethoxycarbonyl-L-lysine (AECK) by using an orthogonal tRNA/synthetase pair from the archaea *Methanosarcina mazei* in a mammalian cell-free system for the first time, as well as in a cell-based system. Using the cell-free system, we show the efficient one-step synthesis of radiolabeled and ready-to-click antibody. Using cell-based expression, we investigated the developability of an antibody-drug conjugate and we proof the position-specific coupling of DBCO-PEG3-MMAE to cell-based produced AECK labeled antibodies by hydrophobic interaction chromatography.

(24) Does the widely used cannabinoid, cannabidiol cause double-strand breaks on human cells? | Lana Taha, Nick Zschoche and Stefan Rödiger | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | lana_taha@web.de

Cannabidiol (CBD) is a substance mainly extracted from the plant *Cannabis sativa*. Due to its positive pharmacological properties, CBD has gained importance lately. CBD is believed to have analgesic, anti-epileptic and even antitumor effects. In June 2018, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration approved the first CBD-based drug, Epidiolex. However, the mode of action and side effects of CBD have not yet been extensively researched. There are studies that demonstrate the cytotoxic effects of CBD. There are also reports that this cannabinoid causes DNA damage (single strand breaks, apurinic sites) even at low dosages. Objective one was to find out if CBD has a toxic effect on immortal human tumor cells with epithelial morphology and causes double strand breaks (DSB) in them. Cannabinoids are poorly soluble in water, and various organic solvents have been described in the literature. Therefore, objective two was a systematic solvent comparison. CBD and the solvents were studied in tumor cell lines and investigated using molecular and cell biological methods (Western blot, proliferation assay, immunofluorescence). In WST-8 assay, HEp-2 and FaDu cell lines showed the highest survivability in DMSO (105%) and EtOH (96%) by WST-8 metabolization. CaCo-2 cells showed high survivability in 1% (v/v) solvent, with WST-8 metabolization of 109.8% (EtOH), 100.6% (MeOH), 96% (isopropanol), and 89.6% (DMSO). CBD in EtOH or DMSO has a toxic effect on all cell lines used. Cytotoxicity assays using MeOH as solvent were not reproducible. Protein expression analysis by Western blot (WB) did not yield results. The DSB biomarkers H2AX and 53BP1 showed a positive control signal in the indirect immunofluorescence assay (AKLIDES® Nuk Kit). We could not confirm the DNA damage postulated in the literature. Since we could not detect DSB damage by combining solvents with CBD, we cannot confirm the DNA damage reported in the literature. The experimental conditions of the methods used in our work from the literature need to be further standardized to automatically perform the analysis of DSBs by high-throughput imaging.

(25) Fully automated viability and toxicity screening - a reliable all-in-one attempt | Victoria Liedtke, Romano Weiss, Anastasia Skifov, Stefan Rödiger, Lysann Schenk | BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg | victoria.liedtke@b-tu.de

Background: The CRISPR/Cas9 technology is nowadays a common tool for genome editing to achieve new insights into, e.g., diagnostics and therapeutics in cancer and genetic disorders. Cell proliferation and anti-cancer drug response studies are widely used to evaluate the impact of editing. However, these assays are often time-consuming, expensive and reproducibility is an issue. To overcome this, we developed a fast and cheap assay that combines a fully automated multispectral fluorescence microscopy platform with a nuclei staining and open source software analysis. Methods: Here, we generated different LEDGF/p75 model cell lines to validate the effect on proliferation and chemosensitivity. Therefore, a fast protocol for an optimized all-in-one attempt for cytotoxicity screenings and proliferation analysis of adherent cells in a 96-well plate format was established using differential staining with two fluorescent dyes (Hoechst 33342 and propidium iodide) for live/dead cell discrimination. Subsequently, an automated cell nuclei count and analysis was performed using bioimage informatics. Results: With the new established assay technology, up to 50000 cells/well can be detected and analyzed in a 96-well plate, resulting in a fast and accurate verification of viability and proliferation with consistency of 98 % compared to manual counting. Our screening revealed that LEDGF depletion using CRISPR/Cas9 showed a diminished proliferation and chemosensitivity independent of cell line origin. Moreover, LEDGF depletion caused a significant increase in

(26) Analysis of albumin fatty acid binding efficiency as a global tumor marker using electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy (EPR) | Katja Waterstradt and Kerstin Schnurr | MedInnovation GmbH | k.waterstradt@medinnovation.de

Early detection of cancer increases the chance of successful treatment for patients. Using a blood test could further increase acceptance of people to participate in early-detection-programs. Albumin-functionality-test is a blood test which is able to detect most of the cancer types (global tumor marker). It analyses the fatty acid binding efficiency of serum albumin using a spin labeled fatty acid (16-doxy-stearic acid) and electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy (EPR). Clinical studies have shown that in patients with active tumor growth, a modified binding characteristic can be detected for that fatty acid. An integral discrimination function (DR – Diagnostic Result) can be calculated from the parameters achieved from the EPR spectra and is used to differentiate patients with active tumor growth from those without with high sensitivity (approximately 90%) at high specificity (approximately 90%). In patients with malignant and benign colorectal diseases, a clear correlation between the DR value and the malignancy and the risk to malignant degeneration is recognizable. A current multicenter, prospective study will validate previous results on the 10 most frequent cancer types and enables the addition of information on tumor localization. Thus, we believe that albumin-functionality-test might be a valuable tool for tumor diagnostic.

(27) Analysis of DNA-damaging potential of the cannabinoid CP 55,940 using the foci detection pipeline NucDetect | Romano Weiss, Victoria Liedtke and Stefan Rödiger | NA | romano.weiss@b-tu.de

Detection of foci formed around DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs) is an important tool for the assessment of DNA damage caused by, among other factors ionizing radiation or chemical agents and thus is of high value for biomedical research. Several tools for semi- or fully automatic foci detection were developed recently, which might require z-stack images, parameter fine-tuning by the user or extensive pre-processing to work optimally. Especially the latter proofs difficult for researchers inexperienced in bioimage informatics. We built a software with a new approach to automatic foci detection, which relies on singular fluorescence images as well as minimal user input. The NucDetect software is built on top of a trained neural network in conjunction with image processing to detect nuclei and foci. We use the presented software to analyze DSB formation after the exposure to the cannabinoid model substance CP 55,940, compare the obtained results to the commonly used chemotherapeutic etoposide and test the cell proliferation and cytotoxicity of CP 55,940.

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Notes